

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Characteristics and outcomes of COVID-19 patients with COPD from the United States, South Korea, and Europe

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Supplementary table S1. Age and gender distribution of hospitalized COVID-19 patients with COPD.

Characteristic	CU-AMC HDC % (95%CI)	CUIMC % (95%CI)	HealthVerity % (95%CI)	IQVIA-OpenClaims % (95%CI)	OptumEhr % (95%CI)	VA-OMOP % (95%CI)	HIRA % (95%CI)	SIDIAP % (95%CI)
age group: <50	4.4%	3.5%	2.0%	3.2%	2.0%	1.3%	14.4%	0.2%
age group: 50-54	<3.3%	1.3%	1.2%	2.4%	2.1%	1.4%	8.3%	0.5%
age group: 55-59	10.7%	5.6%	7.7%	6.2%	9%	4.9%	9.7%	4.1%
age group: 60-64	11%	9.8%	12.1%	11%	14.2%	11.1%	11%	7.8%
age group: 65-69	14.7%	12.5%	16.9%	13.5%	14.9%	15.1%	9%	10.1%
age group: 70-74	15.4%	14.3%	18.5%	15.4%	15.5%	27.2%	16.6%	14.5%
age group: 75-79	14.4%	13.4%	16.4%	14.9%	13.2%	16.4%	12.4%	17.3%
age group: 80-84	12.7%	17.4%	14.7%	13.2%	12.6%	8.2%	11.7%	17.3%
age group: 85-89	12.4%	12.8%	-	20.2%	16.5%	7.7%	6.9%	17.1%
age group: 90-94	4.3%	6.3%	10.5%	-	-	4.6%	<3.4%	8.4%
age group: 95-99	<3.3%	3.1%	-	-	-	1.9%		2.5%
female	41.5%	43.2%	53.2%	47.8%	46.1%	3.3%	42.8%	45.5%
male	58.5%	56.8%	46.8%	52.2%	53.9%	96.7%	57.2%	54.5%

Grey =US database. Pink=South Korean database. Yellow=European database.

Supplementary table S2. Age and gender distribution of diagnosed COVID-19 patients with COPD.

	CU-AMC HDC % (95%CI)	CUIMC % (95%CI)	HealthVerity % (95%CI)	IQVIA-OpenClaims % (95%CI)	OptumEhr % (95%CI)	STARR-OMOP % (95%CI)	VA-OMOP % (95%CI)	CPRD % (95%CI)	IPCI % (95%CI)	SIDIAP % (95%CI)	LPD-FRANCE % (95%CI)	LPDItaly % (95%CI)
Systemic corticosteroids	24.6 (21.5-27.9)	12.9 (10.7-15.4)	8.3 (7.6-9.0)	10.9 (10.7-11.1)	11.9 (11.3-12.5)	20.6 (15.8-26.5)	13.8 (13.2-14.4)	26.4 (21.4-32.1)	23.0 (17.7-29.3)	13.9 (13.4-14.4)	5.1 (3.7-7.1)	10.3 (7.5-14.0)
Inhaled corticosteroid	23.1 (20.1-26.4)	6.9 (5.3-8.9)	11.7 (10.9-12.5)	13.1 (12.8-13.4)	12.2 (11.6-12.8)	11.5 (7.9-16.4)	27.4 (26.6-28.2)	44.8 (38.9-50.9)	27.0 (21.3-33.5)	27.7 (27.0-28.4)	17.0 (14.3-20.1)	5.3 (3.4-8.2)
SABA	26.6 (23.4-30.0)	11.7 (9.6-14.2)	10.6 (9.9-11.4)	13.1 (12.8-13.4)	16.4 (15.7-17.1)	13.8 (9.8-19.0)	25.8 (25.0-26.6)	47.9 (41.9-53.9)	9.5 (6.2-14.4)	10.8 (10.3-11.3)	<0.8	3.8 (2.2-6.4)
SAMA	14.0 (11.6-16.8)	6.6 (5.1-8.6)	4.0 (3.5-4.5)	4.3 (4.2-4.4)	8.0 (7.5-8.5)	11.0 (7.5-15.8)	9.8 (9.3-10.3)	<1.9	12.0 (8.2-17.2)	18.4 (17.8-19.0)	<0.8	3.8 (2.2-6.4)
LABA	16.9 (14.3-19.9)	5.0 (3.7-6.8)	9.7 (9.0-10.4)	9.2 (9.0-9.4)	9.0 (8.5-9.6)	4.6 (2.5-8.2)	18.8 (18.1-19.5)	51.3 (45.3-57.3)	36.0 (29.7-42.9)	24.4 (23.7-25.1)	17.0 (14.3-20.1)	4.7 (2.9-7.5)
LAMA	10.4 (8.3-12.9)	1.0 (0.5-2.0)	4.4 (3.9-4.9)	5.2 (5.0-5.4)	6.0 (5.6-6.5)		13.7 (13.1-14.3)	43.3 (37.4-49.4)	28.0 (22.2-34.6)	14.8 (14.2-15.4)	8.0 (6.2-10.3)	3.5 (2.0-6.0)
Mucolytics	2.3 (1.4-3.7)	<0.6	0.5 (0.4-0.7)	0.2 (0.2-0.2)	0.9 (0.7-1.1)	2.8 (1.3-5.9)	1.2 (1.0-1.4)	17.6 (13.5-22.7)	5.5 (3.1-9.6)	9.7 (9.2-10.2)	13.6 (11.2-16.4)	16.5 (12.9-20.8)
Beta-lactam penicillin	7.2 (5.5-9.4)	4.8 (3.5-6.6)	2.5 (2.1-2.9)	3.7 (3.6-3.8)	3.9 (3.5-4.3)	6.4 (3.9-10.5)	4.6 (4.2-5.0)	20.7 (16.2-26.0)	12.0 (8.2-17.2)	7.7 (7.3-8.1)	5.2 (3.7-7.2)	6.2 (4.1-9.3)
Fluoroquinolones	5.3 (3.9-7.2)	3.6 (2.5-5.2)	2.3 (2.0-2.7)	3.6 (3.5-3.7)	2.6 (2.3-2.9)	5.5 (3.2-9.4)	2.8 (2.5-3.1)	<1.9	<2.5	6.6 (6.2-7.0)	2.3 (1.4-3.8)	7.4 (5.1-10.7)
Macrolides	8.5 (6.6-10.8)	8.4 (6.6-10.6)	5.9 (5.3-6.5)	9.0 (8.8-9.2)	7.1 (6.6-7.6)	5.0 (2.8-8.8)	5.2 (4.8-5.6)	9.2 (6.3-13.3)	7.5 (4.6-12.0)	5.5 (5.2-5.9)	5.4 (3.9-7.4)	7.1 (4.8-10.3)
Acetaminophen	25.7 (22.6-29.1)	18.7 (16.1-21.6)	4.9 (4.4-5.4)	7.3 (7.1-7.5)	16.9 (16.2-17.6)	23.4 (18.3-29.4)	22.8 (22.1-23.5)	47.1 (41.1-53.1)	9.5 (6.2-14.4)	53.5 (52.7-54.3)	31.6 (28.1-35.3)	3.2 (1.8-5.7)
NSAIDs	44.9 (41.2-48.6)	6.6 (5.1-8.6)	4.8 (4.3-5.3)	18.3 (18.0-18.6)	6.6 (6.2-7.1)	5.5 (3.2-9.4)	43.9 (43.0-44.8)	16.9 (12.8-21.9)	5.5 (3.1-9.6)	8.4 (8.0-8.8)	36.6 (33.0-40.4)	17.6 (13.9-22.0)
Opioids	26.0 (22.9-29.4)	8.2 (6.5-10.3)	4.5 (4.0-5.0)	7.9 (7.7-8.1)	10.1 (9.6-10.7)	20.6 (15.8-26.5)	11.5 (10.9-12.1)	17.6 (13.5-22.7)	15.5 (11.1-21.2)	15.8 (15.2-16.4)	8.2 (6.3-10.6)	6.5 (4.3-9.6)
Oxygen	4.3 (3.0-6.1)	<0.6	1.5 (1.2-1.8)	1.3 (1.2-1.4)	0.0 (0.0-0.0)		1.0 (0.8-1.2)	<1.9		0.0 (0.0-0.0)		<1.5

Grey =US database. Pink=South Korean database. Yellow=European database.

Supplementary table S3. Prevalence of treatments in patients with COPD in the 30 days before COVID-19 diagnosis.

SAMA=short-acting muscarinic antagonist. SABA=short-acting beta2-agonist. LAMA=Long-acting muscarinic antagonist. LABA=Long-acting beta2-agonist. ICS=inhaled corticosteroids. NSAIDs=non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Grey =US database. Pink=South Korean database. Yellow=European database.

Characteristic	CU-AMC HDC % (95%CI)	CUIMC % (95%CI)	HealthVerity % (95%CI)	IQVIA- OpenClaims % (95%CI)	OptumEhr % (95%CI)	STARR- OMOP % (95%CI)	VA-OMOP % (95%CI)	CPRD % (95%CI)	IPCI % (95%CI)	SIDIAP % (95%CI)	LPD- FRANCE % (95%CI)	LPD-Italy % (95%CI)
age group: <50	3.8%	3.8%	2.4%	4.4%	3.4%	7.3%	2.6%	2.7%	5.0%	0.8%	6.9%	1.6%
age group: 50-54	1.7%	2.3%	2.4%	2.9%	2.8%	<2.3%	2.5%	<1.9%	<2.5%	1%	4.9%	2.6%
age group: 55-59	10%	7.5%	13.4%	7.3%	10.7%	11.5%	6.4%	4.2%	6.5%	7.1%	16.2%	5.9%
age group: 60-64	12.7%	11.3%	19.3%	11.5%	16.6%	11%	13.5%	6.9%	9.5%	10.5%	19.1%	10.6%
age group: 65-69	15.3%	13.6%	17.1%	13%	15.5%	18.8%	16.1%	10.3%	9%	9.3%	15.3%	12.4%
age group: 70-74	16.3%	16.5%	15.1%	14.1%	14.4%	22%	27.7%	15.3%	17%	11.2%	16.5%	17.1%
age group: 75-79	13.7%	12.6%	12.7%	13.4%	12.1%	15.1%	14.6%	16.9%	17%	12.4%	9.1%	13.2%
age group: 80-84	11.3%	14.2%	10.2%	12%	10.3%	8.3%	6.6%	23.4%	14%	13.4%	5.9%	16.2%
age group: 85-89	9%	10.3%	-	21.4%	14.2%	6%	5.5%	12.6%	18%	16.5%	4.2%	12.4%
age group: 90-94	4.8%	5.2%	7.4%	-	-	<2.3%	3%	7.7%	4%	12.3%	1.9%	5.9%
age group: 95-99	1.4%	2.7%	-	-	-	-	1.3%	<1.9%	<2.5%	4.7%	<0.8%	2.1%
female	48.7%	46.8%	58.5%	51.9%	51.5%	41.7%	5.4%	50.6%	48.5%	57.8%	54%	43.8%
male	51.3%	53.2%	41.5%	48.1%	48.5%	58.3%	94.6%	49.4%	51.5%	42.2%	45.5%	43.8%

Supplementary table S4. Prevalence of outcomes in diagnosed COVID-19 patients with COPD with 95%CI.

	CU-AMC HDC % (95%CI)	CUIMC % (95%CI)	HealthVerity % (95%CI)	IQVIA-OpenClaims % (95%CI)	OptumEhr % (95%CI)	STARR-OMOP % (95%CI)	VA-OMOP % (95%CI)
Intensive services	13.3 (11.0-16.0)	1.2 (0.6-2.2)	1.3 (1.0-1.6)	6.2 (6.0-6.4)	6.8 (6.3-7.3)	4.1 (2.2-7.6)	5.7 (5.3-6.1)
ARDS	30.9 (27.6-34.4)	10.3 (8.3-12.7)	6.0 (5.4-6.6)	18.4 (18.1-18.7)	19.4 (18.7-20.2)	8.7 (5.6-13.2)	15.3 (14.7-15.9)
ARFS	16.8 (14.2-19.8)	10.1 (8.2-12.4)	4.9 (4.4-5.4)	12.2 (12.0-12.4)	18.5 (17.8-19.2)	11.0 (7.5-15.8)	13.6 (13.0-14.2)
Cardiac arrhythmia	20.1 (17.3-23.2)	7.7 (6.0-9.8)	3.2 (2.8-3.7)	7.1 (6.9-7.3)	14.5 (13.9-15.2)	7.8 (4.9-12.1)	12.3 (11.7-12.9)
Heart failure	13.0 (10.7-15.7)	5.1 (3.8-6.9)	3.2 (2.8-3.7)	5.3 (5.1-5.5)	9.4 (8.9-10.0)	10.6 (7.2-15.4)	9.3 (8.8-9.8)
Pulmonary edema	12.3 (10.1-15.0)	3.9 (2.8-5.5)	2.2 (1.9-2.6)	5.4 (5.2-5.6)	6.8 (6.3-7.3)	2.3 (1.0-5.3)	3.3 (3.0-3.6)
Myocardial infarction	3.9 (2.7-5.6)	0.9 (0.4-1.8)	0.6 (0.4-0.8)	1.6 (1.5-1.7)	3.3 (3.0-3.6)		2.2 (2.0-2.5)
Sepsis	17.1 (14.5-20.1)	4.3 (3.1-6.0)	3.3 (2.9-3.8)	9.8 (9.6-10.0)	9.9 (9.4-10.5)	5.0 (2.8-8.8)	6.6 (6.2-7.0)
Bleeding	6.6 (5.0-8.7)	3.2 (2.2-4.7)	2.0 (1.7-2.4)	2.9 (2.8-3.0)	5.9 (5.5-6.3)	4.1 (2.2-7.6)	3.7 (3.4-4.0)
VThE	5.2 (3.8-7.1)	3.2 (2.2-4.7)	1.1 (0.9-1.4)	1.7 (1.6-1.8)	3.5 (3.2-3.9)	4.1 (2.2-7.6)	3.2 (2.9-3.5)
PE	2.7 (1.7-4.2)	1.8 (1.1-3.0)	0.8 (0.6-1.0)	1.2 (1.1-1.3)	2.1 (1.8-2.4)	<2.3	1.9 (1.7-2.1)
Stroke	<1.4	1.6 (0.9-2.8)	0.5 (0.4-0.7)	1.0 (0.9-1.1)	1.4 (1.2-1.6)	<2.3	1.4 (1.2-1.6)

Data for the primary care databases CPRD, IPCI, SIDIAP, LPD-France and LPD-Italy not shown as incomplete capture. VTHE=venous thromboembolism. PE=pulmonary edema. MI=myocardial infarction. ARFS=Acute renal failure syndrome. ARDS=Acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Grey =US database. Pink=South Korean database. Yellow=European database.*

Supplementary figure S1. Flow chart showing database selection.

Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD), Daegu Catholic University Medical Center (DCMC), Health Insurance Review & Assessment Service (HIRA), Information System for Research in Primary Care (SIDIAP), Tufts Research Data Warehouse (TRDW), Department of Veterans Affairs (VA-OMOP), Integrated Primary Care Information (IPCI), Columbia University Irving Medical Center (CUIMC), University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus Health Data Compass (CU-AMC HDC). *No prior observation period available.

Supplementary figure S2. Prevalence of age and gender among COPD patients with COVID-19 who have been diagnosed (red) and hospitalized (blue).

*Databases contributing patients to both the diagnosed and hospitalized cohorts.

Supplementary figure S3. Comparison of characteristics between COPD patients with COVID-19 in the diagnosed and hospitalized cohorts by SMD.

*Databases contributing patients to both the diagnosed and hospitalized cohorts. SMD less than 0 = More prevalent in the hospitalized patients. SMD greater than 1 = More prevalent in the diagnosed cohort. Age groups measured in years. T2DM=Type 2 diabetes mellitus. CVD=Cerebrovascular disease. CKD=chronic kidney disease. Autoimmune Cond.=autoimmune conditions.

APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Overview of Data Sources Screened for Eligibility and Contributing Results

Database Name	Country	Description	Contributed By
Clinical Practice Research Datalink	United Kingdom	The Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) is a governmental, not-for-profit research service, jointly funded by the NHS National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) and the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA), a part of the Department of Health, United Kingdom (UK). CPRD consists of data collected from UK primary care for all ages. This includes conditions, observations, measurements, and procedures that the general practitioner is made aware of in addition to any prescriptions as prescribed by the general practitioner. In addition to primary care, there are also linked secondary care records for a small number of people. The major data elements contained within this database are outpatient prescriptions given by the general practitioner (coded with Gemscript codes) and outpatient clinical, referral, immunization or test events that the general practitioner knows about (coded in Read or ICD10 or LOINC codes). The database also contains the patients' year of births and any date of deaths. The cohorts represented in this application were run on a COVID-specific cut of the CPRD database which included patients with a SARS-CoV-2 test, diagnosis, or related code.	Janssen Research & Development, Titusville, NJ, USA
University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus Health Data Compass (CU-AMC HDC)	United States	Health Data Compass (HDC) is a multi-institutional data warehouse. HDC contains inpatient and outpatient electronic medical data including patient, encounter, diagnosis, procedures, medications, laboratory results from two electronic medical record systems (UCHealth and Children's Hospital of Colorado), state-level all-payers claims data, and the Colorado death registry. Acknowledgement statement: Supported by the Health Data Compass Data Warehouse project (healthdatacompass.org).	

Columbia University Irving Medical Center	United States	The clinical data warehouse of NewYork-Presbyterian Hospital/Columbia University Irving Medical Center, New York, NY, based on its current and previous electronic health record systems, with data spanning over 30 years and including over 6 million patients	Department of Biomedical Informatics, Columbia University Irving Medical Center, New York, NY 10032, USA
Daegu Catholic University Medical Center	South Korea	A teaching hospital in Daegu, South Korea, covered by Federated E-health Big Data for Evidence Renovation Network (FEEDER-NET).	Department of Biomedical Sciences, Ajou University Graduate School of Medicine, Suwon, Korea
HealthVerity	United States	This HealthVerity derived data set contains de-identified patient information with an antibody and/or diagnostic test for COVID-19 linked to all available Medical Claims and Pharmacy Data from select private data providers participating in the HealthVerity marketplace.	Janssen Research & Development, Titusville, NJ, USA
Health Insurance Review & Assessment Service (HIRA)	South Korea	National claim data from a single insurance service from South Korea. It contains the observational medical records (including both inpatient and outpatient) of a patient while they are qualified to get the national medical insurance.	Health Insurance Review & Assessment Service, 60 Hyeoksin-Rho, Wonju-Si, Gangwon- Do(Bangkok- Dong), 26465, Korea

HM Hospitals	Spain	Hospital de Madrid (HM) Hospitals data are made available through partnership with IDIAPJGol. The HM Hospitals database covers in-patient care delivered across a network of 17 private hospitals in Spain between 1st of March and 24th of April 2020. HM Hospitals database covers more than 2300 confirmed COVID-19 cases, and all in-patient hospital care, including the data of admission, conditions, procedures and medicines dispensed in hospital, date of discharge, and date of known death or date of end of follow-up in the database.	Fundacio Institut Universitari per a la recerca a l'Atencio Primaria de Salut Jordi Gol i Gurina (IDIAPJGol), Barcelona, Spain
Integrated Primary Care Information (IPCI)	Netherlands	The Integrated Primary Care Information (IPCI) database is a Dutch database containing the medical records of more than 2.5 million patients provided by more than 600 GPs geographically spread over the Netherlands. In the Netherlands, all citizens are registered with a GP practice which acts as a gatekeeper in a two-way exchange of information with secondary care.	Department of Medical Informatics, Erasmus University Medical Center, Rotterdam, The Netherlands
IQVIA Open Claims		A United States database of open, pre-adjudicated claims from January 2013 to May 2020. Data are reported at anonymized patient level collected from office-based physicians and specialists via office management software and clearinghouse switch sources for the purpose of reimbursement. A subset of medical claims data have adjudicated claims.	Real World Solutions, IQVIA Inc, Cambridge, MA, USA
IQVIA Disease Analyser Germany (DA Germany)	Germany	IQVIA DA Germany is collected from extracts of patient management software used by GPs and specialists practicing in ambulatory care settings. Data coverage includes more than 34M distinct person records out of total population of 80M (42.5%) in the country and collected from 2,734 providers. Dates of service include from 1992 through March 2020.	Real World Solutions, IQVIA Inc, Cambridge, MA, USA
LDP France	France	LPD France is a computerised network of physicians including GPs who contribute to a centralised database of anonymised patient EMR. Currently, >1200 GPs from 400 practices are contributing to the database covering 7.8M patients in France. The database covers a time period from 1994 through the present. Observation time is defined by the first and last consultation dates. Drug information is	Real World Solutions, IQVIA Inc, Cambridge, MA, USA

		derived from GP prescriptions. Drugs obtained over the counter by the patient outside the prescription system are not reported.	
LDP Italy	Italy	LPD Italy is comprised of anonymised patient records collected from software used by GPs during an office visit to document patients' clinical records. Data coverage includes over 2M patient records with at least one visit and 119.5M prescription orders across 900 GP practices. Dates of service include from 2004 through present. Observation time is defined by the first and last consultation dates. Drugs are captured as prescription records with product, quantity, dosing directions, strength, indication and date of consultation.	Real World Solutions, IQVIA Inc, Cambridge, MA, USA
Nanfeng Hospital COVID-19 Research Database (NFHCRD)	China	The clinical data warehouse of The People's Hospital of Hong Hui Hubei China based on its current and previous electronic health record systems, with data spanning over 4 months and including over 400 patients.	Nanfeng Hospital, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, China; DHC Technologies Co. Ltd. Beijing, China
Optum EHR	United States	Optum© de-identified Electronic Health Record Dataset represents Humedica™s Electronic Health Record data a medical records database for patients receiving a COVID-19 diagnosis record or lab test for SARS-CoV-2. The medical record data includes clinical information, inclusive of prescriptions as prescribed and administered, lab results, vital signs, body measurements, diagnoses, procedures, and information derived from clinical Notes using Natural Language Processing (NLP).	Janssen Research & Development, Titusville, NJ, USA
Premier Healthcare Database	United States	The Premier Healthcare Database contains complete clinical coding, hospital cost, and patient billing data from approximately 700 hospitals throughout the United States representing 20% of inpatient hospital stays. Premier collects data from participating hospitals in its health care alliance. The Premier health care alliance was formed for hospitals to share knowledge, improve patient safety, and reduce risks. Participation in the Premier health care alliance is voluntary. Although the database excludes federally funded hospitals (e.g., Veterans Affairs), the	Janssen Research & Development, Titusville, NJ, USA

		hospitals included are nationally representative based on bed size, geographic region, location (urban/rural) and teaching hospital status. The database contains a date-stamped log of all billed items by cost-accounting department including medications; laboratory, diagnostic, and therapeutic services; and primary and secondary diagnoses for each patient hospitalization.	
Information System for Research in Primary Care (SIDIAP)	Spain	The Information System for Research in Primary Care (SIDIAP; www.sidiap.org) is a primary care records database that covers approximately 7 million people, equivalent to an 80% of the population of Catalonia, North-East Spain. Healthcare is universal and tax-payer funded in the region, and primary care physicians are gatekeepers for all care and responsible for repeat prescriptions.	Fundacio Institut Universitari per a la recerca a l'Atencio Primaria de Salut Jordi Gol i Gurina (IDIAPJGol), Barcelona, Spain
Information System for Research in Primary Care Hospitalization Linked Data (SIDIAP-H)	Spain	The Information System for Research in Primary Care (SIDIAP; www.sidiap.org) is a primary care records database from Catalonia, North-East Spain. The SIDIAP-H subset of the database includes around 2 million people out of the total 7 million in SIDIAP that are registered in primary care practices with linked hospital inpatient data available as obtained from the Catalan Institute of Health hospitals. Healthcare is universal and tax-payer funded in the region, and primary care physicians are gatekeepers for all care and responsible for repeat prescriptions.	Fundacio Institut Universitari per a la recerca a l'Atencio Primaria de Salut Jordi Gol i Gurina (IDIAPJGol), Barcelona, Spain
Stanford medicine Research data Repository (STARR-OMOP)	United States	STanford medicine Research data Repository, a clinical data warehouse containing live Epic data from Stanford Health Care, the Stanford Children's Hospital, the University Healthcare Alliance and Packard Children's Health Alliance clinics and other auxiliary data from Hospital applications such as radiology PACS. STARR platform is developed and operated by Stanford Medicine Research IT team and is made possible by Stanford School of Medicine Research Office.	Department of Medicine, School of Medicine, Stanford University, Redwood City, CA USA
Tufts Research Data Warehouse (TRDW)	United States	Electronic medical record data on approximately 1 million patients who received care beginning in 2006 at Tufts Medical Center (TMC). TMC is an academic medical center that includes Tuft Medical Center's main downtown Boston hospital for adult patients, the Floating Hospital for	Tufts Institute for Clinical Research and Health Policy

		Children, and associated primary and specialty care clinics. TRDW contains TMC's EHR data fused with data on the same patients from TMC's CoC accredited tumor registry, its oncology EHR, and death data from the Massachusetts State Registry of Vital Statistics. EHR data streams ingested into TRDW include controlled vocabulary data on all domains except cost, and select free text sources and devices.	Studies, Boston, MA, 02111, USA
United States Department of Veterans Affairs	United States	VA OMOP data reflects the national Department of Veterans Affairs health care system, which is the largest integrated provider of medical and mental health services in the United States. Care is provided at 170 VA Medical Centers and 1,063 outpatient sites serving more than 9 million enrolled Veterans each year.	VA Informatics and Computing Infrastructure, VA Salt Lake City Health Care System, Salt Lake City, UT, USA; Tennessee Valley Healthcare System, Veterans Affairs Medical Center, Nashville, TN, USA

Appendix 2. Definitions and codes used to identify COVID-19

The full description of the logic used to define diagnosed patients is provided at <https://atlas.ohdsi.org/#/cohortdefinition/200>. Similarly, the full description of the logic used to identify patients hospitalized is provided at <https://atlas.ohdsi.org/#/cohortdefinition/197>.

2.1 COVID-19 condition codes

Concept id	Concept name	Vocabulary
756023	Acute bronchitis due to COVID-19	OMOP Extension
756044	Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) due to COVID-19	OMOP Extension
756061	Asymptomatic COVID-19	OMOP Extension
756031	Bronchitis due to COVID-19	OMOP Extension
439676	Coronavirus infection	SNOMED
37311061	Disease caused by 2019-nCoV	SNOMED

4100065	Disease due to Coronaviridae	SNOMED
37310284	Encephalopathy caused by 2019 novel coronavirus	SNOMED
37310283	Gastroenteritis caused by 2019 novel coronavirus	SNOMED
4248811	Healthcare associated severe acute respiratory syndrome	SNOMED
756081	Infection of lower respiratory tract due to COVID-19	OMOP Extension
37310286	Infection of upper respiratory tract caused by 2019 novel coronavirus	SNOMED
45763594	Middle East respiratory syndrome	SNOMED
37310287	Myocarditis caused by 2019 novel coronavirus	SNOMED
37310254	Otitis media caused by 2019 novel coronavirus	SNOMED
37310285	Pneumonia caused by 2019 novel coronavirus	SNOMED
37016927	Pneumonia caused by Human coronavirus	SNOMED
40479642	Pneumonia due to Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus	SNOMED
756039	Respiratory infection due to COVID-19	OMOP Extension
320651	Severe acute respiratory syndrome	SNOMED
37396171	Severe acute respiratory syndrome of upper respiratory tract	SNOMED
37311060	Suspected disease caused by 2019-nCoV	SNOMED

2.2 COVID-19 specific testing - Positive

Concept id	Concept name	Vocabulary
37310282	2019 novel coronavirus detected	SNOMED

2.3 COVID-19 specific testing (note, these required a corresponding value as concept of: Detected, Positive, or Present)

Concept id	Concept name	Vocabulary
37310255	Detection of 2019 novel coronavirus using polymerase chain reaction technique	SNOMED
700360	Infectious agent detection by nucleic acid (DNA or RNA); severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (Coronavirus disease [COVID-19]), amplified probe technique	CPT4
37310258	Measurement of 2019 novel coronavirus antibody	SNOMED
37310257	Measurement of 2019 novel coronavirus antigen	SNOMED
756055	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)	OMOP Extension
586310	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) Genetic material using Molecular method	OMOP Extension

704991	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in Blood	OMOP Extension
756029	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in Respiratory specimen	OMOP Extension
586307	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in Saliva	OMOP Extension
705107	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in Sample from nose	OMOP Extension
586309	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in Specified specimen	OMOP Extension
756065	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in Unspecified specimen	OMOP Extension
704992	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Culture method	OMOP Extension
705001	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Nucleic acid amplification technique	OMOP Extension
705000	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Nucleic acid amplification technique in Blood	OMOP Extension
756085	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Nucleic acid amplification technique in Respiratory specimen	OMOP Extension
586308	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Nucleic acid amplification technique in Saliva	OMOP Extension
705106	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Nucleic acid amplification technique in Sample from nose	OMOP Extension
756084	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Nucleic acid amplification technique in Unspecified specimen	OMOP Extension
704993	Measurement of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) using Sequencing	OMOP Extension
586516	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by Organism specific culture	LOINC
723480	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) Ab [Interpretation] in Serum or Plasma	LOINC
586515	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) Ab [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
586522	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) Ab [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
706179	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) Ab panel - Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
723477	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) Ag [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by Rapid immunoassay	LOINC
706166	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) E gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC

586523	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) E gene [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
586518	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) E gene [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706174	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) E gene [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723473	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgA Ab [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
586521	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgA Ab [Presence] in Serum, Plasma or Blood by Rapid immunoassay	LOINC
723459	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgA Ab [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
757686	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgA+IgM [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
586527	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgG Ab [Presence] in DBS by Immunoassay	LOINC
723474	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgG Ab [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
706181	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgG Ab [Presence] in Serum, Plasma or Blood by Rapid immunoassay	LOINC
706177	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgG Ab [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
706176	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgG and IgM panel - Serum, Plasma or Blood by Rapid immunoassay	LOINC
723479	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgG+IgM Ab [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
723475	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgM Ab [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
706180	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgM Ab [Presence] in Serum, Plasma or Blood by Rapid immunoassay	LOINC
706178	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) IgM Ab [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma by Immunoassay	LOINC
706167	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706157	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by Nucleic acid amplification using CDC primer-probe set N1	LOINC
706155	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by Nucleic acid amplification using CDC primer-probe set N2	LOINC
715272	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Nasopharynx by NAA with probe detection	LOINC

757678	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Nose by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706161	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
586524	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by Nucleic acid amplification using CDC primer-probe set N1	LOINC
586525	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by Nucleic acid amplification using CDC primer-probe set N2	LOINC
586520	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706175	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706156	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by Nucleic acid amplification using CDC primer-probe set N1	LOINC
706154	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) N gene [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by Nucleic acid amplification using CDC primer-probe set N2	LOINC
757680	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) neutralizing antibody [Presence] in Serum by pVNT	LOINC
757679	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) neutralizing antibody [Titer] in Serum by pVNT	LOINC
723469	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) ORF1ab region [Cycle Threshold #] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706168	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) ORF1ab region [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723478	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) ORF1ab region [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723464	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) ORF1ab region [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723471	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RdRp gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723470	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RdRp gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706160	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RdRp gene [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706173	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RdRp gene [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
586528	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Cycle Threshold #] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
586529	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC

715262	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Log #/volume] (viral load) in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723476	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Nasopharynx by NAA with non-probe detection	LOINC
586526	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Nasopharynx by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
757677	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Nose by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706163	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
715260	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Saliva (oral fluid) by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
715261	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Saliva (oral fluid) by Sequencing	LOINC
723463	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706170	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706158	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA panel - Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
706169	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) RNA panel - Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723467	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) S gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723468	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) S gene [Cycle Threshold #] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723465	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) S gene [Presence] in Respiratory specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
586519	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) S gene [Presence] in Serum or Plasma by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
723466	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) S gene [Presence] in Unspecified specimen by NAA with probe detection	LOINC
586517	SARS-CoV-2 (COVID19) whole genome [Nucleotide sequence] in Isolate by Sequencing	LOINC
40218805	Testing for SARS-CoV-2 in CDC laboratory	HCPCS
40218804	Testing for SARS-CoV-2 in non-CDC laboratory	HCPCS

Appendix 3. Definitions and codes used to identify COPD patients

3.1 Definitions used to identify COPD patients

Group	Concept id	Concept name	Vocabulary
Asthma diagnosis (for exclusion)	252658	Intrinsic asthma without status asthmaticus	SNOMED
	252942	Asthmatic pulmonary eosinophilia	SNOMED
	256448	Chronic asthmatic bronchitis	SNOMED
	257581	Exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
	257583	Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis	SNOMED
	312950	IgE-mediated allergic asthma	SNOMED
	313236	Cough variant asthma	SNOMED
	317009	Asthma	SNOMED
	443801	Exercise-induced asthma	SNOMED
	761844	Inhaled steroid-dependent asthma	SNOMED
	764677	Persistent asthma	SNOMED
	764949	Persistent asthma, well controlled	SNOMED
	2108536	Persistent asthma, preferred long term control medication or an acceptable alternative treatment, prescribed (NMA-No Measure Associated)	CPT4
	4022592	Millers' asthma	SNOMED
	4051466	Childhood asthma	SNOMED
	4057952	Meat-wrappers' asthma	SNOMED
	4075237	Brittle asthma	SNOMED
	4080516	Printers' asthma	SNOMED
	4081994	Tropical pulmonary eosinophilia	SNOMED
	4110051	Mixed asthma	SNOMED
	4119298	Late onset asthma	SNOMED
	4119300	Colophony asthma	SNOMED
	4120261	Sulfite-induced asthma	SNOMED
4120262	Cryptogenic pulmonary eosinophilia	SNOMED	
4123253	Hay fever with asthma	SNOMED	
4125022	Acute asthma	SNOMED	

4138760	Exacerbation of intermittent asthma	SNOMED
4141978	Intermittent asthma	SNOMED
4142738	Moderate persistent asthma	SNOMED
4143474	Bakers' asthma	SNOMED
4143828	Mild persistent asthma	SNOMED
4145356	Severe persistent asthma	SNOMED
4145497	Intrinsic asthma	SNOMED
4146581	Mild intermittent asthma	SNOMED
4152913	Severe asthma	SNOMED
4155468	Mild asthma	SNOMED
4155469	Moderate asthma	SNOMED
4155470	Occasional asthma	SNOMED
4191479	Allergic asthma	SNOMED
4206340	Asthma without status asthmaticus	SNOMED
4211530	Asthma caused by wood dust	SNOMED
4212099	Occupational asthma	SNOMED
4217558	Detergent asthma	SNOMED
4225553	Cheese-makers' asthma	SNOMED
4225554	Isocyanate induced asthma	SNOMED
4232595	Platinum asthma	SNOMED
4233784	Asthmatic bronchitis	SNOMED
4235703	Asthma management	SNOMED
4244339	Drug-induced asthma	SNOMED
4245292	Weavers' cough	SNOMED
4245676	Chemical-induced asthma	SNOMED
4250128	Aspirin-induced asthma	SNOMED
4271333	Allergic asthma without status asthmaticus	SNOMED
4277596	Simple pulmonary eosinophilia	SNOMED
4279553	Eosinophilic asthma	SNOMED
4301938	Tea-makers' asthma	SNOMED

4309833	Non-IgE mediated allergic asthma	SNOMED
4312524	Substance induced asthma	SNOMED
35609846	Life threatening acute exacerbation of extrinsic asthma	SNOMED
35609847	Life threatening acute exacerbation of non-allergic asthma	SNOMED
36684328	Acute severe exacerbation of allergic asthma	SNOMED
36684335	Exacerbation of allergic asthma due to infection	SNOMED
37108580	Severe controlled persistent asthma	SNOMED
37108581	Severe uncontrolled persistent asthma	SNOMED
37109103	Oral steroid-dependent asthma	SNOMED
37116845	Acute severe refractory exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
37206717	Near fatal asthma	SNOMED
37208352	SAFS - severe asthma with fungal sensitisation	SNOMED
37310241	Intermittent allergic asthma	SNOMED
40481763	Acute exacerbation of chronic asthmatic bronchitis	SNOMED
40483397	Seasonal asthma	SNOMED
42535716	Asthma in pregnancy	SNOMED
42536207	Life threatening acute exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
42536208	Moderate acute exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
42536649	Uncomplicated non-allergic asthma	SNOMED
42538744	Exacerbation of allergic asthma	SNOMED
42539549	Uncomplicated allergic asthma	SNOMED
43530693	Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive airways disease with asthma	SNOMED
43530745	Asthma with irreversible airway obstruction	SNOMED
44783610	Asthma self management	SNOMED
44810117	Chronic asthma with fixed airflow obstruction	SNOMED
44810118	Eosinophilic bronchitis	SNOMED
45757063	Allergic bronchopulmonary mycosis	SNOMED
45766727	Allergic asthma due to Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus	SNOMED
45766728	Allergic asthma due to Dermatophagoides farinae	SNOMED
45768910	Uncomplicated asthma	SNOMED

45768911	Exacerbation of mild persistent asthma	SNOMED
45768912	Exacerbation of severe persistent asthma	SNOMED
45768963	Uncomplicated mild persistent asthma	SNOMED
45768964	Uncomplicated moderate persistent asthma	SNOMED
45768965	Uncomplicated severe persistent asthma	SNOMED
45769350	Acute severe exacerbation of severe persistent asthma	SNOMED
45769351	Acute severe exacerbation of moderate persistent asthma	SNOMED
45769352	Acute severe exacerbation of mild persistent asthma	SNOMED
45769438	Acute severe exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
45769441	Acute exacerbation of allergic asthma	SNOMED
45769442	Acute severe exacerbation of immunoglobulin E-mediated allergic asthma	SNOMED
45769443	Acute severe exacerbation of intrinsic asthma	SNOMED
45771045	Acute exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
45772073	Asthma in mother complicating childbirth	SNOMED
45772937	Exacerbation of moderate persistent asthma	SNOMED
45773005	Acute exacerbation of intrinsic asthma	SNOMED
46269767	Acute severe exacerbation of asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
46269770	Severe persistent allergic asthma	SNOMED
46269771	Acute severe exacerbation of severe persistent asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
46269776	Mild persistent allergic asthma	SNOMED
46269777	Acute severe exacerbation of mild persistent allergic asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
46269784	Moderate persistent allergic asthma	SNOMED
46269785	Acute severe exacerbation of moderate persistent asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
46269801	Aspirin exacerbated respiratory disease	SNOMED
46269802	Chronic obstructive asthma co-occurrent with acute exacerbation of asthma	SNOMED
46270028	Severe persistent asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
46270029	Mild persistent asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED

	46270030	Intermittent asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
	46270082	Acute exacerbation of mild persistent asthma	SNOMED
	46270322	Intermittent asthma uncontrolled	SNOMED
	46273452	Acute exacerbation of asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
	46273454	Moderate persistent asthma co-occurrent with allergic rhinitis	SNOMED
	46273462	Acute severe exacerbation of moderate persistent allergic asthma	SNOMED
	46273487	Acute exacerbation of moderate persistent asthma	SNOMED
	46273635	Steroid dependent asthma	SNOMED
	46274059	Acute severe exacerbation of severe persistent allergic asthma	SNOMED
	46274062	Asthma-chronic obstructive pulmonary disease overlap syndrome	SNOMED
	46274124	Acute severe exacerbation of mild persistent allergic asthma	SNOMED
COPD diagnosis (target population)	255573	Chronic obstructive lung disease	SNOMED
	257004	Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive airways disease	SNOMED
	258780	Emphysematous bronchitis	SNOMED
	259043	Emphysematous bleb of lung	SNOMED
	261325	Pulmonary emphysema	SNOMED
	261895	Compensatory emphysema	SNOMED
	440748	Interstitial emphysema of lung	SNOMED
	3185549	Bronchiectasis with acute exacerbation	Nebraska Lexicon
	4046986	End stage chronic obstructive airways disease	SNOMED
	4050732	Pulmonary emphysema in alpha-1 PI deficiency	SNOMED
	4050733	Toxic emphysema	SNOMED
	4050734	Scar emphysema	SNOMED
	4050961	Giant bullous emphysema	SNOMED
	4056405	Obstructive emphysema	SNOMED
	4083395	Vanishing lung	SNOMED
	4104506	Cystic-bullous disease of the lung	SNOMED
	4110048	Chronic bullous emphysema	SNOMED
	4110056	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute lower respiratory infection	SNOMED

4110635	Segmental bullous emphysema	SNOMED
4112828	Zonal bullous emphysema	SNOMED
4112836	Chronic emphysema due to chemical fumes	SNOMED
4115044	Acute infective exacerbation of chronic obstructive airways disease	SNOMED
4136683	Paraseptal emphysema	SNOMED
4138392	Chronic obliterative bronchiolitis due to inhalation of chemical fumes AND/OR vapors	SNOMED
4145496	Bullous emphysema with collapse	SNOMED
4148124	Atrophic (senile) emphysema	SNOMED
4166508	Congenital emphysema	SNOMED
4166517	Chronic obliterative bronchiolitis	SNOMED
4177944	Panacinar emphysema	SNOMED
4193588	Moderate chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	SNOMED
4196712	Mild chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	SNOMED
4209097	Severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	SNOMED
4246105	Hemolytic anemia with emphysema AND cutis laxa	SNOMED
4278831	Chronic diffuse emphysema due to inhalation of chemical fumes AND/OR vapors	SNOMED
4286497	Centriacinar emphysema	SNOMED
4315386	Ruptured emphysematous bleb of lung	SNOMED
43530693	Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive airways disease with asthma	SNOMED
44791725	Very severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	SNOMED
44807895	Acute non-infective exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	SNOMED
45769389	Pulmonary emphysema co-occurrent with fibrosis of lung	SNOMED
46269701	Chronic obstructive lung disease co-occurrent with acute bronchitis	SNOMED
46270376	Acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive bronchitis	SNOMED
46274062	Asthma-chronic obstructive pulmonary disease overlap syndrome	SNOMED

3.2 Medications used to define COPD diagnosis and treatments

	Concept id	Concept name	Vocabulary
Long-acting beta agonists	43024344	vilanterol Inhalation Powder	RxNorm Extension
	43180317	vilanterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	1356189	salmeterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	783089	salmeterol Inhalation Solution	RxNorm Extension
	35158799	salmeterol Inhalation Powder	RxNorm Extension
	40167702	salmeterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	45775117	olodaterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	21174574	olodaterol Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	40746100	olodaterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	44055847	indacaterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	1356211	indacaterol Inhalation Powder	RxNorm
	42479568	indacaterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	1356187	formoterol Inhalation Solution	RxNorm
	1356191	formoterol Inhalation Powder	RxNorm
Short-acting beta agonists	36812414	Terbutaline Inhalation Solution	RxNorm Extension
	36813480	Terbutaline Inhalation Powder	RxNorm Extension
	40152687	pirbuterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	41205378	pirbuterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	40143276	levalbuterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	1356103	levalbuterol Inhalation Solution	RxNorm
	40142703	albuterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	1356108	albuterol Inhalation Solution	RxNorm
	1356111	albuterol Inhalation Powder	RxNorm
	46234463	albuterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	41142750	umeclidinium Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	43285708	umeclidinium Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	45774869	umeclidinium Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	45774773	tiotropium Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm

Long-acting muscarinic antagonist	1356250	tiotropium Inhalation Powder	RxNorm
	42482607	tiotropium Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	42482075	tiotropium Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	35149223	glycopyrronium Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	1356202	glycopyrronium Inhalation Solution	RxNorm
	1356199	glycopyrronium Inhalation Powder	RxNorm
	43292583	glycopyrronium Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	43179057	glycopyrronium Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	41236953	aclidinium Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	44069324	aclidinium Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	42873412	aclidinium Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
Inhaled corticosteroids	44817882	mometasone Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	40892816	Mometasone Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	36894464	Mometasone Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	40143326	mometasone Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	40144037	fluticasone Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	41080160	fluticasone Injectable Solution	RxNorm Extension
	35149212	fluticasone Inhalation Solution	RxNorm Extension
	35147990	fluticasone Inhalation Powder	RxNorm Extension
	40144035	fluticasone Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	44120754	Budesonide Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	1356140	budesonide Inhalation Suspension	RxNorm
	35135829	Budesonide Inhalation Solution	RxNorm Extension
	1356143	budesonide Inhalation Powder	RxNorm
	40142920	budesonide Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	40142784	beclomethasone Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	35130061	Beclomethasone Inhalation Solution	RxNorm Extension
	36883710	Beclomethasone Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	42480194	Beclomethasone Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
		40223712	formoterol / mometasone Metered Dose Inhaler

Combo-therapy	41267401	fluticasone / vilanterol Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	43291091	fluticasone / vilanterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	43532281	fluticasone / vilanterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	37592046	fluticasone / vilanterol / vilanterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	40755794	fluticasone / umeclidinium / vilanterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	792484	fluticasone / umeclidinium / vilanterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	40144024	fluticasone / salmeterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	42482744	fluticasone / salmeterol Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	36882733	fluticasone / salmeterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	40144020	fluticasone / salmeterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm
	21089505	fluticasone / formoterol Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	40754973	fluticasone / formoterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	41048760	fluticasone / formoterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	36787269	Budesonide / salmeterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	40142910	budesonide / formoterol Metered Dose Inhaler	RxNorm
	783228	Budesonide / formoterol Inhalation Solution	RxNorm Extension
	35133500	Budesonide / formoterol Inhalation Powder	RxNorm Extension
	42479684	Budesonide / formoterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	21090035	Beclomethasone / formoterol Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	36894458	Beclomethasone / formoterol Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	21158944	Beclomethasone / formoterol Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	36787954	Beclomethasone / formoterol / glycopyrronium Inhalant Solution	RxNorm Extension
	40745353	Beclomethasone / formoterol / glycopyrronium Inhalant Powder	RxNorm Extension
	36421291	Beclomethasone / formoterol / glycopyrronium Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension
	36250078	azelastine / fluticasone Metered Dose Nasal Spray	RxNorm
	36812530	Albuterol / Beclomethasone Inhalation Powder	RxNorm Extension
	42483138	Albuterol / Beclomethasone Dry Powder Inhaler	RxNorm Extension